

European Navigation Conference

Warsaw 9 - 12 April 2019

Autonomous Indoor & Outdoor Safety Tracking System

NIOSA

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OVERVIEW
Some AIOSAT numbers are presented

CONCEPT
AIOSAT approach

ARCHITECTURE
AIOSAT architecture explanation

POSITIONING
Technologies used for tracking

FUSION
Brief introduction to the Particle Filter

SUMMARY
Conclusion and future steps

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European Global Navigation Satellite Systems Agency

Results incorporated in this project received funding from the European GNSS Agency under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776425.

Autonomous Indoor & Outdoor Safety Tracking System

Project information

AIOSAT

Grant agreement ID: 776425

Status: Ongoing project

Start date: 1 December 2017 | End date: 31 May 2020

Funded under:
 H2020-EU.3.2.1.
 H2020-EU.2.1.6.3.
 H2020-EU.2.1.6.1.2.

Overall budget: € 2 032 650

EU contribution: € 1 764 262,50

Coordinated by:
 ASOCIACION CENTRO TECNOLOGICO CEIT-
 IK4
 Spain

Total Budget: 2,032,650.00 €
 EU contribution: 1,764,262.50 €

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OVERVIEW

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- Number of participants: 7 from 3 countries
- Covering all areas:
 - Technology Providers (SAXION, CEIT-IK4, RMS-KMS)
 - Engineering service providers (INTEGRASYS)
 - Subsystem manufacturers (INERTIA)
 - End-users (TSC, FRS CENTRUM)

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OVERVIEW

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European Forest Fire Information System (EFFIS):

<http://effis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

Fires in Europe per year:

- 2'000'000 fires
- 5'000 fire related deaths
- 50'000 injured
- 10-20 billion euros of damage

The overarching objective of AIOSAT system is to advance beyond the state of the art in tracking rescue workers by creating a high availability and high integrity team tracking and alerting system.

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OVERVIEW

Horizontal accuracy:

Indoor : which room compartment

Outdoor : 5 to 10 m

Vertical accuracy:

Indoor : determinate the floor level of FF

Outdoor : 10 m

Robustness: work in at least 9/10 cases

Tracking system update frequency: as fast as possible

Accepted a general *update frequency of 10 sec*

In rural interventions can be 1 – 5 minutes

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TRUCK

TRUCK

ICP: Incident Command Post
SO: Subofficer
FR: First Responder

SO

FR1

FR2

SO

FR1

FR2

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CONCEPT

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ARCHITECTURE

GNSS based position determination

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CONCEPT

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ARCHITECTURE

$AUG = f(AUGMENTATION)$
 RTCM 3.1 (1004) -> 1001/1002

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CONCEPT

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ARCHITECTURE

GNSS

TRUCK

P. REPORT

P. REPORT

ICP

FUSION ALGORITHM (PARTICLE FILTER)
P. REPORT = (GNSS, AUG, PDR, UWB)

EDAS

FR1

P. REPORT

SO

FR2

P. REPORT

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CONCEPT

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GNSS

TRUCK

INFO & ALERT

ICP

INFO & ALERT

SO

INFO = EVACUATION PATH + EVENTS

ALERT = EVACUATION

EDAS

FR1

ALERT

FR2

ALERT

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CONCEPT

GNSS	PDR	UWB
Individual node absolute position	Individual node relative displacement	Distance between a pair of nodes
<ul style="list-style-type: none">NoisyNo indoor signalConditions-sensitive	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Bearing biasBearing drift	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Low-rangeDependent valuesTransmission medium

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FUSION

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ARCHITECTURE

- ① GNSS receiver (u-blox® NEO-M8T)
- ② UWB transceiver (Decawave® DWM1001)
- ③ PDR module (Inertia ProMove MINI)
- ④ LORA/LTE module (pycom® fipy®)
- ⑤ Bluetooth 5 module (Nordic® NRF52840)

VISUALIZATION

- First responders tracking real-time
- Quality factors monitoring (Temp, Comms., GNSS)
- Role identification
- Real-time events notifications
- Record & Replay

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VISUALIZATION

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Safety

Improvement of safety of the operations

Fusion

Multi-sensor approach algorithm (particle filter)

GNSS

Enhanced GNSS positioning using augmentation

Visualization

Tracking and alerting application

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FUTURE STEPS

- Extremadura, Spain
 - Rural scenario
 - Forest fire – Mixed conditions for open sky
- Ghent, Belgium
 - Urban scenario – underground
 - Fire in a multilevel underground car park
- Enschede, The Netherlands
 - Two urban scenarios
 - Fire in a complex multistory residential building
 - Fire + explosion in a large industrial building

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FIELD-TESTS

Rural Scenario - Spain

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FIELD-TESTS

Urban underground
Belgium

Dimension parking:

- 1 command vehicle (officer and driver)
- 2 pump truck (driver + chief + 4 firemen)
- 2 specialist fire trucks (driver + 2 firemen)

Sub-off: 3

On board: 6 6 3 3

Firemen: 6 6 3

FIELD-TESTS

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Complex building
Netherlands

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FIELD-TESTS

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Thank you for your attention!

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Autonomous Indoor & Outdoor Safety Tracking System

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Robust, reliable, long range links, even in harsh indoor environments and rubble

Automatic configuration (easy and fast deployment) of the radio network

Sufficient bandwidth to support the AIOSAT related communications (positioning reporting and alerting)

Low latency, to ensure that there is rapid action or knowledge of the status

Support of Quality of Service (QoS)

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OVERVIEW

Configurable position reporting from firefighters using messaging delivery over the communication network with payload optimization

Guaranteed, real-time delivery of safety warnings using messaging delivery over the communication network with payload optimization

Measurement and report firefighter time spent on a given area (e.g. within a building)

Basic indoor mapping capability (building limits) obtained from public spatial information sources such as cadastral databases

The weight of the sensor should be as low as possible (1 kg)

The sensor should be as small as possible, so as to not disturb the normal motion of the firefighter

The system should operate at least 12h (missing in action)

The working temperature of the sensor should be between -10°C and +85°C, but should tolerate 100°C without being damaged

The sensor can resist a fall of 10 meter. Resistant to hit and shocks

